

COMPARISON OF THE ANTIMICROBIAL EFFECT OF THREE NATURAL PRODUCTS FORMULATED AS A GEL DOSAGE FORM

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ABSTRACT

Background: Nowadays, there is an increase in the incidence of life-threatening bacterial infections accompanied by antimicrobial failure due to different reasons including multidrug resistance. There is a huge effort to find new compounds to treat this problem which should have no toxicity on humans with specific activity on bacteria and should demonstrate acceptable bioavailability. The pathway to find such compound is long and expensive. However, natural compounds or compounds derived from natural products represent a good alternative.

Aims: This work has selected three different natural products which are known for their antimicrobial effects, and investigated their antimicrobial effects on different types of microbes including Gram-positive bacteria, Gram-negative bacteria and fungi.

Materials and Methods: The exudate and two extracts of three natural products include *Aloe vera*, *Glycyrrhiza glabra*, and Propolis, were prepared and incorporated into Carbomer-934 as a gelling agent, and propylene glycol as a plasticizer to form N-1, N-2, and N-3 formulae containing the aforesaid natural substances, respectively. Antimicrobial susceptibility *in-vitro* tests of the selected formulae were studied against different types of microbes. Then, the three mentioned products were subjected to an additional *in-vitro* susceptibility test against the three common microorganisms (*Staphylococcus aureus*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, and *Candida albicans*). Moreover, stability studies for their physicochemical properties were conducted longer than six months after their production.

Results and Discussion: The study findings demonstrated no significant difference ($p \leq 0.05$) in physicochemical properties among all three formulae and for each formula before and after storage at room temperature for six months. Selection of the best antimicrobial natural product may be not that simple to decide because results showed a significant difference ($p \leq 0.05$) in the *in-vitro* susceptibility tests for N-1 before and after storage at room temperature for six months; however, the susceptibility test of (N-2 and N-3) revealed persistence of some antimicrobial effectiveness against microbes especially *Staphylococcus aureus*.

Conclusion and recommendations:

Aloe vera gel containing exudate (N-1) may not be very stable and therefore not very efficient against microbes. The gels prepared from Liquorice and Propolis extracts (N-2 and N-3) are often very efficient antimicrobials on *Staphylococcus aureus*, which appears to be the most susceptible organism. The antibacterial activity, especially against *Candida* species, could be diminished with time after the preparation of the gels. More research should be done to develop natural antimicrobial gels that are more stable over time so they can be used as substitutes for commercial products.

Keywords: *Aloe vera*, Liquorice, Propolis, gel, antimicrobial activity, *Staphylococcus aureus*.

Introduction

Historically, the use of natural products for treating human diseases was very long. Several plant species have been used in several cultures such as *Aloe vera* which is a member of the lily plant known as *Aloe barbadensis* which was used therapeutically, nearly 6000 years ago in Egypt. The antimicrobial effect might be attributed to the plant's natural anthraquinones constituent.(1) Another plant species is Liquorice (*Glycyrrhiza glabra*) and which was mentioned in the clay tablets from ancient Mesopotamia in 2600 BC; such plants (roots) are still used either alone or as one of the components of herbal formulations for the treatment of various diseases including treatment of infection. Furthermore, Propolis (bee glue), which is made from plant-based materials-resins and was extensively utilized by the ancient Greeks, Romans, and Egyptians who were familiar with the healing properties of Propolis and made great use of it as a medicine. Propolis contains high concentrations of polyphenols and flavonoids, which might be responsible for various activities. Generally, Propolis is used by both bee's feral colonies in tree cavities and domesticated colonies in commercial hive boxes, for covering holes and gaps in the nest, and restricting the hive entrance which is clear from the origin of the word Propolis ("Pro": in front of; "polis": the city). Utilizing Propolis in this manner by bees is thought to function as a way for colonies to better maintain homeostasis of the nest environment. This could be a result of decreasing microbial growth on hive walls and waterproofing the walls against external moisture, in addition to providing some protection against intruders. (2,3) These traditional and important natural sources of medicines were shown in figure1.

Figure (1) some important natural sources of medicines

Gel dosage forms (sometimes known as Jellies) are semisolid systems consisting of either suspension made up of small inorganic particles or large organic molecules included in a liquid. Gels are classified as two-phase system or single-phase systems. (4) Gels of Single-phase consist of organic macromolecules evenly distributed throughout a liquid in such a way that no apparent boundaries exist between the dispersed macromolecules and the liquid. Single-phase gels may be formulated using synthetic macromolecules (e.g. Carbomer) or natural gums (e.g., Tragacanth). (5) Natural medicinal ingredients such as extracts or exudates may be incorporated in carbomer-based gels to be formulated a gel dosage form which can be used to deliver medication topically or into the body.(6–8)

Topical skin infections commonly occur and frequently give therapeutic challenges to professionals, despite the numerous existing antimicrobials available today. Common examples of topical skin infections include diaper rash which is a type of irritant contact dermatitis, mouth sores, and tinea (also known as pityriasis) versicolor, acne, and eczema. In addition, any burn or wound may result in skin infection. The need to develop new antimicrobial agents has increased significantly due to growing concerns about multidrug-resistant strains of bacteria, viruses, and fungi (8).

Consequently, in the field of antimicrobial chemotherapy, attention has been paid to safe, new, and/or alternative antimicrobial materials.

In previously published works of our lab, new formulae of (*Aloe vera*, Liquorice, and Propolis gel), were prepared and evaluated successfully and from each work a product was selected that met all the required criteria of topical gel as well as for their good antimicrobial effects.(6,7)

This work aims to compare these three natural products in terms of their antimicrobial effect against two different types of bacteria including *Staphylococcus aureus* (as a Gram- positive bacteria) and *Pseudomonas aerogenosae* (as a Gram- negative bacteria) and against *Candida albicans* as fungus in order to select the best one which may be used for burn wound infections or other types of skin infections.

Materials

Materials for preparing the three natural products: The fresh *Aloe vera* (*Aloe barbadensis*) leaves and the dried coarse powder of Liquorice root were purchased from the local market in Mosul City, Iraq. Propolis samples were collected from honey bee beehives in the city of Babylon, Iraq during the 2017 and 2018 spring seasons. Carbomer-934 was purchased from (HIMEDIA, India). Ethanol, sodium sulphite, and triethanolamine were obtained from (Tedia, USA). Propylene glycol was purchased from (THOMAS BAKER Co., India). All other chemicals were of analytical grade.

Methods

Production of the three products

Carbomer-934 gel formula was prepared as published earlier with some modifications. During the preparation procedure, Carbomer-934 dispersions were prepared by adding little amount of distilled water (D.W.) to the polymer with slight hand-mixing and then stirred by using a magnetic stirrer (Fisher Scientific, Korea) at moderate speed with slight heating at about 50-55°C for 2-3 hours. The Carbomer-934 dispersion was cooled and covered with a piece of aluminum foil overnight to remove air bubbles. The following day, the calculated amount of each of the natural substances (*Aloe vera* exudate, extracts of Liquorice, and Propolis) was added separately for the above mentioned dispersion, stirred using the magnetic stirrer, completed the volumes with D.W. and then sufficient quantities of triethanolamine was added as a final step of preparation to get the three natural gel products designed as (N-1, N-2, and N-3, respectively) and the resulting formulae were wrapped with aluminum foil and placed in the refrigerator. (6,7,9)

All physicochemical tests, including those to measure pH , viscosity, torque, spreadability, appearance, consistency, colour and odor, were carried out in accordance with the methodology published earlier. (6,7)

Antimicrobial effects of the three products

In-vitro antimicrobial effects

Susceptibility Test

Antimicrobial susceptibility effects of the selected formula (N-1) were studied against bacterial species including *Staphylococcus aureus* (gram+) and *Escherichia coli* (gram-) and for the selected formulae (N-2 and N-3) were also studied by well diffusion method against bacterial species including *Staphylococcus aureus* (gram+), *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (gram-), and against one fungal type which is *Candida Albicans*. A 39 g of Muller-Hinton agar was diluted with 1 Liter of D.W. to prepare Mueller-Hinton agar (Lab M, UK). The mixture was stirred, brought to a boil using a hot plate stirrer (Stuart, UK), then autoclaved for 15 minutes at 115°C using a portable autoclave (Guangzhou, China). The prepared agar was then transferred onto a petri dish to cool and solidify and then a 6 mm diameter well inside the prepared agar was made. With a concentration of 0.5 McFarland standard (1.5x10⁸ CFU/ml), fresh cultures of *Staphylococcus aureus* (*Staph.aureus*), *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (*Pseud.aeruginosa*), and *Candida albicans* (*C.albicans*) were prepared by adding and spreading the necessary bacterial suspension on the top of the agar plates with a sterile cotton swab. Standard antibiotic discs were used as a positive control and placebo polymer gel was used as a negative control. After 15 minutes, 100 µl of the three prepared natural gel formulae were added to the resulting wells. Then the plates were incubated aerobically at 37°C for 24 hours for bacteria and also at 37°C for 48 to 72 hours for yeast. (6,10)

Stability study for the three products

The prepared gels (N-1, N-2, and N-3) which were incorporated with the three natural substances were tested for stability. Well-closed containers were used for six months of stability testing at 25°C. The prepared gels were assessed for their physicochemical characteristics after six months, including their appearance, color, homogeneity, consistency, lack of clogs or aggregates, pH , viscosity, spreadability. The antimicrobial properties were also examined to ensure the gels' efficiency against gram positive and gram negative bacteria in addition to the yeast, by which D.W. was used for gel dilutions (as four concentrations of the gel were prepared: 25. 50. 75, and 100%). The positive control employed was (Streptomycin 25 g, Ciprofloxacin 10 g,

and Nystatin 30 g) discs, whereas the negative control was carbomer-934-based gel without any integration with a natural material.(11)

Selecting the best antimicrobial product

The potential for an antimicrobial effect, along with good physicochemical stability, were the criteria used to select the best antimicrobial formula among the three natural products (N-1, N-2, and N-3). This was done by studying an additional test of antimicrobial effectiveness of the three above products against the three common microbes (*Staph.aureus*, *Pseud.aeroginosa*, and *C.albicans*) which was carried out after approximately more than 6 months from the products' preparations.

Statistical Analysis

The results were taken as mean \pm standard deviation and statistically analyzed using *t-test*. A value of $p \leq 0.05$ was considered significant.

Results and Discussion

The Physicochemical Properties

The physicochemical properties of the prepared natural gels (N-1 and N-2) were measured according to the established procedure published earlier (6,7). In addition, the prepared natural gel (N-3) was measured according to another procedure mentioned in a recent work (submitted to be published) and all the three natural products (N-1, N-2, and N-3) exhibited good characteristics, as demonstrated in Table 1.

Table1. Physicochemical properties of the three natural products containing *Aloe vera exudate*, liquorice extract, and Propolis extract with their assigned batch codes, N-1, N-2, and N-3 respectively (All values are expressed as mean \pm SD, n = 3)

Measured parameters	N-1	N-2	N-3
pH	5.40 \pm 0.5	5.50 \pm 0.5	5.70 \pm 0.09
Viscosity (Pa.s)	122.846 \pm 0.14	112.750 \pm 0.25	132.880 \pm 0.16
Spreadability (mg.cm/s)	26.0-27.2	0.45-0.89	5.15-6.23
Appearance	Good	Good	Good
Colour	Pale-pink	Dark- brown	Golden brown
Homogeneity and consistency	Smooth	Smooth	Smooth
Removal	Easy	Easy	More sticky

Antimicrobial effects of the three products

In-vitro antimicrobial effects (Susceptibility Test)

Staph. aureus is a typical pathogen that causes infections of the soft tissues and musculoskeletal system. The three formulae (N-1, N-2, and N-3), were used to investigate the antimicrobial efficacy against different types of microorganisms including *Staph.aureus*.

The results of antimicrobial effect of *Aloe vera* are presented in table 2 and figure 2. The measurement of inhibition zone of *Aloe vera* exudate gel product (N-1) against both *Staph.aureus* and *E.coli* was in the range of (0-30 mm) with higher antibacterial activity against *Staph.aureus*. (7) These findings corroborated those of V.C. Pawar *et al.*, who found that using *Aloe vera* gel extract completely inhibited the growth of *Staph.aureus*.(12) Additionally, Sahu RK *et al* findings, which compared various plant extracts, including *Aloe vera*, against various types of bacteria, including *E. coli*, reported that the majority of bacterial species were susceptible to all *Aloe vera* extracts when used in high concentrations and this is in agreement with our findings.(13) In addition, some other studies indicated that the use of *Aloe Vera* leaf and root ethanol extracts can be used in conjunction with traditional antibiotics to combat the infection-causing chemicals that are so common in skin infections.(14)

Indeed, it is expected that the results from using of *Aloe vera* exudate is going to be not in accordance with the results of using extract. In addition, the type of solvents in the extraction process, the methodology and other variables like the time of extraction and method of purification have a pronounced effect on the product and its efficacy against different microbes. Concerning Liquorice, the results, which are presented in table 3 revealed that natural Liquorice gel product (N-2) had a preferable antimicrobial activity against *Staph.aureus* and *C.albicans* with zone of inhibition ranged from (0-25) mm for *Staph. aureus*, while for *C.albicans* the zone of inhibition varied from (0–10) mm in comparison with control.(6) However no antimicrobial activity was detected against the gram-negative bacteria *Pseud.aeroginosa*(6), which showed higher resistance to the product N-2 than the tested Gram-positive bacteria and yeast. Because *Pseud.aeroginosa* is a type of bacteria that is assumed to be multi-drug resistant, the distinction between (Gram-positive) and (Gram-negative) bacteria's cell membrane structures may help to explain this. (15)

Results also indicated that the prepared Liquorice gel product (N-2) had higher antimicrobial effect against *Candida* species than against the tested bacterial species with zone of inhibition for *Staph.aureus* ranged from (0-25) mm, while for *C.albicans* (12-30) mm. Supportive results were obtained from work conducted by Karahana *et al* in 2016. (16) Their research demonstrated that Liquorice had an anti-bacterial action utilizing the disc agar diffusion method. The zone of inhibition for *Staph.aureus* ranged from (12-19) mm, but there was no anti-bacterial activity against *Pseud.aeroginosa*. In 2013, Geetha and Anitha demonstrated that the diameter of the Liquorice-treated *C.albicans* zone of inhibition ranged from (9-20) mm.(17).

This antifungal effect of Liquorice against candida might be attributed to the presence of licochalcone A and glabridin, two isoflavonoids derived from Liquorice. These two showed a fungicidal action on *candida albicans* at relatively low minimum inhibitory concentrations.(18) Regarding the antimicrobial effect of the prepared Propolis gel product, which are demonstrated in table 4 and figure 4; product N-3 effect was investigated toward (*Staph. aureus*, *Pseudo. aeruginosa* and *enterococcus fecalis*) and fungi (*C.albican*). Results showed large inhibition of the growth of *C. Albicans* (13.7mm) and showed (15.5, 12 and 13.2 mm) zones of inhibitions towards *Staph. aureus*, *Pseudo. aeruginosa* and *enterococcus fecalis*, respectively. The effectiveness of Propolis extract in gel formula against *Staph.aureus* was previously screened by Kehribar L,S, *et al.* (2021) who indicated that incorporation of Propolis extract into gel formula would improve the antibacterial effectiveness of Propolis against different kinds of bacteria. (19) The antifungal effectiveness of Propolis in gel dosage form was previously studied by many researchers including Berretta AA *et al* (2013) who developed many gel-based formulae containing different Propolis extracts and studied their use in preclinical treatment of candidiasis vulvovaginal infection and came to the conclusion that *in-vivo* efficacy had demonstrated that Propolis-based gels provide antifungal action similar to that of clotrimazole cream. (20)

Stability study for the three products

When the three prepared natural product formulae were kept tightly closed and stored at room temperature for six months, no significant difference ($p \leq 0.05$) in visual appearance, colour, homogeneity, and consistency was observed. Aggregates and clogs were not present. Additionally, after six months of storage, there was no significant difference in the pH, spreadability and viscosity.

Selecting the best antimicrobial product

Results obtained after a period of six months showed that the three products (N-1, N-2, and N-3) revealed good physicochemical stability including: pH, viscosity, spreadability, general appearance, and consistency. However, some contradicting results were found in the antimicrobial efficiency against (*Staph.aureus*, *Pseud.aeruginosa*, and *C.albicans*). The susceptibility test of the *Aloe vera* gel product (N-1) showed resistance (R) to *Staph.aureus*, *Pseudomonas* and *C.albicans* as represented in table 2 and figure2, in all concentrations used.

:Table 2 Susceptibility test for different concentrations of *Aloe vera* gel against different types of microorganisms after six months period at room temperature

Bacteria and Fungus	% Natural gel product (<i>Aloe vera</i> gel)				Control	
	100%	75%	50%	25%	Negative	Positive
	Zone of Inhibition (mm)					
<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	R	R	R	R	R	22.9
<i>Pseudomonas aerogenosa</i>	R	R	R	R	R	14.3
<i>Candida albicans</i>	R	R	R	R	R	21.3

(R): Resistant. Streptomycin, 25Ciprofloxacin 10, and Nystatin 30 as positive controls for testing susceptibility of the gel against *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Pseudomonas aerogenosae* and *Candida albicans*, respectively.

Staph.aureus

Pseudo.aeruginosa

C.albicans

Figure 2: Susceptibility test showed zone of inhibition of different concentrations of *Aloe vera* gel (N-1) against *Staph.aureus*, *Pseudo.aeruginosa*, and *C.albicans*.

Although the susceptibility test of the liquorice gel product (N-2) exhibited resistance (R) to *Pseudomonas* and *C.albicans* in all concentrations utilized following preparation of more than six months at room temperature, a good antibacterial activity was revealed against *Staph.aureus* at 100%(m/v) and to a lesser extent at 75%(m/v) of N2. At 50% (m/v) concentration, there is very little impact, and at 25% (m/v) of the gel, there is none. Table 3 and Figure 3 show same findings for all applied concentrations.

:Table3 Susceptibility test for different concentrations of Liquorice gel against different types of microorganisms after more than six months at room temperature

Bacteria and Fungus	% Natural gel product (Liquorice gel)				Control	
	100%	75%	50%	25%	Negative	Positive
Zone of Inhibition (mm)						
<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	13.3	12	10	R	R	25.1
<i>Pseudomonas aerogenosa</i>	R	R	R	R	R	15.5
<i>Candida albicans</i>	R	R	R	R	R	20.5

(R): Resistant. Streptomycin 25, Ciprofloxacin 10, and Nystatin 30 as positive controls for testing susceptibility of the gel against *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Pseudomonas aerogenosa* and *Candida albicans* respectively.

Figure 3. Susceptibility test showed zone of inhibition of different concentrations of *Liquorice* gel (N-2) against *Staph.aureus*, *Pseudo.aeruginosa*, and *C.albicans*

For Propolis gel product (N-3), at 100%(m/v) concentration, the antimicrobial activity was evident against all of the test microorganisms (*Staph.aureus*, *Pseud.aeruginosa*, and *C.albicans*). Having zones of inhibition that are , 13.3, 10.0, and 13.4 mm, respectively. In contrast, N-3 was only effective against *Staph. aureus* at a concentration of 75% (m/v). Other concentrations (25 and 50%) showed R and had no impact. (Table4 and Figure4)

.: **Table 4** Susceptibility test for different concentrations of *Propolis* gel against different types of microorganisms after six months period at room temperature

Bacteria and Fungus	% Natural gel product (<i>Propolis</i> gel)				Control	
	100%	75%	50%	25%	Negative	Positive
	Zone of Inhibition (mm)					
<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	13.3	12	R	R	R	22.8
<i>Pseudomonas aerogenosa</i>	10.0	R	R	R	R	14.9
<i>Candida albicans</i>	13.4	R	R	R	R	21.6

(R): Resistant. Streptomycin 25Ciprofloxacin 10, and Nystatin 30 as positive controls for testing susceptibility of the gel against *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Pseudomonas aerogenosa* and *Candida albicans* respectively.

Figure4: Susceptibility test showed zone of inhibition of different concentrations of *Propolis* gel (N-3) against *Staph. aureus*, *Pseudo. aeruginosa*, and *C. albicans*.

Conclusion

In general, the three prepared gel products have favorable relationship among them as they are the most important ancient products which had been utilized before thousands of years for their therapeutic properties. All the three prepared gels have distinctive antimicrobial effects especially within the first three months of preparation. After that, there may be decrease in the level of antimicrobial activity particularly against *Candida* species. *Staph. aureus* seems to be the most susceptible organism, and the gels made from Liquorice and Propolis extracts (N-2 and N-3) are particularly efficient antimicrobials on it. *Aloe vera* as gel dosage form should be

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used as an extract rather than an exudate because the latter may have little stability and so little antimicrobial effectiveness. No definitive results could be taken from other studies to support that; however more studies should be conducted to assess these natural products' stability and their effectiveness as antimicrobial products over time. The use of such natural products will still be employed instantly, and supporting studies should be carried out to make it easier to apply them as a substitute of the commercial products.

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